

Using the Ensemble Kalman Filter for Reactivity Estimates in Zero-Power Reactor Startup

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ABSTRACT

During reactor startup, operators typically estimate reactivity with the measured reactor period and assumed or calculated reactor kinetics parameters. As the neutron flux builds up, longer observation times yield more precise period and reactivity estimates, which will always be stricken by some degree of noise. Near criticality, this process becomes time-consuming, particularly when high accuracy is required for criticality experiments. Furthermore, kinetics parameters used to derive reactivity themselves often carry uncertainty from simulations or nuclear data. This study applies the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF) to startup data from the CROCUS reactor to enable real-time reactivity estimation accounting for the noisy measurements of the neutron population and of the uncertain kinetics parameters. The EnKF accurately creates a smoothed estimate of the neutron population and adjusts (both the mean and uncertainty) of the reactivity, delayed neutron fractions, decay constants, and mean generation time. It shows strong robustness to noise and model uncertainty. These results demonstrate that EnKF-based methods can support near-real-time experimental reactor operations and decision making.

Keywords: Experimental Reactor Physics, Data Assimilation, Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF), Reactor Kinetics

1. INTRODUCTION

The startup of a nuclear reactor is a delicate process involving safety, regulatory, and technical constraints. Early startup often relies on inverse multiplication procedures until remote reactivity control becomes necessary [1]. In this remote stage, operators adjust reactivity with control rods, insertion of a moderator (water level), or – in the case of vertical or horizontal lift machines [2] – closing the gap between two halves of an assembly. In remote operations, the neutron population is monitored to estimate the reactor period, which is subsequently leveraged to estimate the system's level of criticality. With critical experiments for code and data validation, very precise measurements close to criticality are required. In this case, long measurement times of tens of minutes are required to achieve sufficiently accurate reactor periods. Undershooting (negative period) can cause significant loss of time because something may need to be changed in the reactor (addition of fuel, moderator, etc.), which means ending remote operations and physically entering the reactor area.

Beyond the constraints of precise period measurements, the derivation of k_{eff} from the reactor period requires knowledge of the reactor's kinetics parameters. These may be estimated by computational methods [3], but then have biases or uncertainties that arise from methods or nuclear data. For online estimates of criticality, the kinetics parameters are another source of bias and uncertainty. The kinetics parameters are associated with the Point Reactor Kinetics (PRK) model describing the time-dependent behavior of nuclear reactors. The PRK equations describe this transient behavior through a system of coupled differential equations representing the neutron population and delayed neutron precursor

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concentrations. These equations incorporate kinetics parameters such as the delayed neutron fractions, delayed neutron precursor concentrations and decay constants, and the mean generation time.

During reactor startup, the neutron population and delayed neutron precursor concentrations change rapidly and nonlinearly, as modeled by the PRK equations. In practice, it is possible to measure reactor power (neutron flux) with instrumentation, but precursor concentrations and reactivity are not directly measurable. Furthermore, this measurement signal is noisy, especially during the early stages of startup in low-power or zero-power systems. Moreover, the kinetics parameters may vary due to geometric perturbation, or due to temperature, control rod motion, and feedback. These variations in the kinetics parameters are typically not accounted for in real-time operations.

Into this context, this paper applies data assimilation methods, specifically the Ensemble Kalman filter (EnKF) [4] to create a recursive estimation framework for reactor startup. Data assimilation helps to update unobserved states with experimental evidence and is then used for more accurate parameter estimation, namely the reactivity. The approach can effectively filter measurement noise from neutron flux signals. Furthermore, it provides a real-time capability for online implementation during reactor operation. Ultimately, the approach may improve reactivity estimates for reactor control maneuvers.

This paper introduces the Kalman filter and specifically the EnKF, and how it was applied to the PRK equations. Next, it applies the implemented EnKF to artificial data to understand numerical effects and then to experimental data from the CROCUS reactor. The EnKF is assessed based on its ability to improve reactivity estimates and to adjust the kinetic parameters and reduce their associated uncertainty.

2. THEORY

2.1. The Ensemble Kalman Filters

Kalman filters are recursive estimation algorithms that infer the state of a system from noisy measurements and a physical model. The simplest linear Kalman filter is equivalent to the optimal least-squares estimator. It estimates n states of the *state vector* or $\mathbf{x}(t_k)$ at each timestep t_k of Eq. (1).

$$\mathbf{x}(t_k) = [x_1 \quad x_2 \quad \dots \quad x_n]^T(t_k) \quad (1)$$

The dynamics are modeled with Eq. (2) where \mathbf{F} is the state transition matrix and \mathbf{Q}_k is the process noise covariance matrix.

$$\mathbf{x}(t_{k+1}) = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{x}(t_k) + \mathbf{w}_k, \quad \mathbf{w}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{Q}_k). \quad (2)$$

Measurements of the system are expressed as Eq. (3) where \mathbf{H} is the observation matrix and \mathbf{R}_k the observation noise covariance matrix.

$$\mathbf{z}_k = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}(t_k) + \mathbf{v}_k, \quad \mathbf{v}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mathbf{R}_k), \quad (3)$$

At each timestep, the filter alternates between two phases: prediction in Eq. (4) and update in Eq. (5).

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} = \mathbf{F}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1|k-1}, \quad \mathbf{P}_{k|k-1} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{P}_{k-1|k-1}\mathbf{F}^T + \mathbf{Q}_k \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{K}_k &= \mathbf{P}_{k|k-1}\mathbf{H}^T \left(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{P}_{k|k-1}\mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{R}_k \right)^{-1}, \\ \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k} &= \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} + \mathbf{K}_k \left(\mathbf{z}_k - \mathbf{H}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} \right), \\ \mathbf{P}_{k|k} &= (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}_k\mathbf{H})\mathbf{P}_{k|k-1} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Here, $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k}$ is the updated state estimate and $\mathbf{P}_{k|k}$ its covariance. This recursive scheme efficiently balances predictions from the model with noisy observations in real time.

The PRK equations are nonlinear, and a linear Kalman filtering is not sufficient. Nonlinear extensions include the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) [5], which linearizes the model and observation operators using Jacobians, and the Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) [6], which propagates carefully chosen sigma-points to better capture nonlinearities. This work specifically sought to characterize the Ensemble Kalman Filter (EnKF) for reactor startup state estimation. The EnKF maintains an ensemble of state realizations using a Monte Carlo approach. Each member is advanced through the nonlinear model F in the prediction step of Eq. (6) and updated using the nonlinear observation operator H of Eq. (7).

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1}^{(i)} = F\left(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1|k-1}^{(i)}, \mathbf{w}_{k-1}^{(i)}, t_{k-1}\right), \quad (6)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k}^{(i)} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1}^{(i)} + \mathbf{K}_k \left[\mathbf{z}_k^{(i)} - H\left(\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1}^{(i)}, 0, t_k\right) \right]. \quad (7)$$

The Kalman gain \mathbf{K}_k is computed from the ensemble statistics, allowing the EnKF to approximate nonlinear dynamics without explicit Jacobians (as in EKF) or sigma-point construction (as in UKF).

2.2. Application to PRK Model

The EnKF was applied to the PRK model with six delayed neutron groups ($N_\ell = 6$), using experimental data from the zero-power reactor CROCUS at EPFL [7], and was implemented within a Python-based simulation tool developed for this study. The data consist of neutron counts as the reactor was brought critical during several step reactivity insertions (42 ± 6 to 165 ± 6 pcm). For this application, Eq. (8) describes the state vector.

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = [n(t), c_1(t), \dots, c_{N_\ell}(t), \rho, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_{N_\ell}, \lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_{N_\ell}, \Lambda]^T \quad (8)$$

The state vector is split into the dynamic variables $\mathbf{d}(t) = [n(t), c_1(t), \dots, c_{N_\ell}(t)]^T$ and the parameter vector $\mathbf{e}(t)$. The PRK equations for the dynamic part can be written in matrix form:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \mathbf{d}(t) = \mathbf{A}(t) \mathbf{d}(t) + \mathbf{q}(t),$$

$$\mathbf{A}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\rho(t) - \beta(t)}{\Lambda(t)} & \lambda_1 & \dots & \lambda_{N_\ell} \\ \frac{\beta_1(t)}{\Lambda(t)} & -\lambda_1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\beta_{N_\ell}(t)}{\Lambda(t)} & 0 & \dots & -\lambda_{N_\ell} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{q}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} q(t) \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

At each timestep, the matrix $\mathbf{A}(t_k)$ is computed using the vector $\mathbf{e}(t_k)$ and the system is numerically solved using the explicit Runge Kutta solver, with process noise applied to the dependent variables. $\mathbf{q}(t)$ represents the neutrons added to the system by an external source. The only observation is the neutron population \mathbf{z}_k , modeled as a Poisson variable approximated as a Gaussian distribution for the EnKF.

The initial state \mathbf{x}_0 is assumed Gaussian, with mean $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{0|0}$. The reactor kinetics parameters were initially estimated from Serpent2.1.21 simulations of the CROCUS reactor [8]. To quantify the uncertainty of the kinetics parameters and create a covariance matrix for the EnKF, nuclear data from ENDF/B-VII.1 were randomly sampled with the tool NUSS [9]. This analysis showed that the delayed neutron fractions

have uncertainties from nuclear data up to 5%, the decay constants and the mean generation time were largely insensitive to nuclear data uncertainties. This effect will appear later in the results of applying the EnKF. Dynamic variables are initialized from the stationary PRK solution, with *a priori* estimates of 50% relative uncertainty. A 50% uncertainty was chosen after experimentation with the numerical stability of the EnKF over the reactor transient.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Control Model

To test the implementation of the EnKF, a synthetic dataset from the PRK equations was generated. This data served as ground truth. The associated kinetics parameters were perturbed, and noise was added to them to represent a likely real-world scenario. Fig. 1 shows an example output of the EnKF for the estimated reactivity and mean generation time, while Fig. 2a presents the estimation of the first and second delayed neutron fractions, and Fig. 2b shows the estimation of the corresponding delayed neutron precursor decay constants. They show how the filter first starts to vary the estimations, before converging to the expected value after 200s while simultaneously decreasing the prior uncertainty. In the presence of observation noise (measurement uncertainty), the estimations became more uncertain and unstable, particularly for the reactivity and kinetic parameters, which are not directly observed (like the neutron population) but estimated via the filter thanks to the model and the measurements. This initially showed that the filter was too sensitive to noisy measurements, leading to fluctuations and unreliable convergence.

Figure 1. EnKF estimate using a Control Model

To mitigate this, the observation noise covariance matrix \mathbf{R}_k was multiplied by a scaling factor r , which reduced the weight of noisy data relative to the physical model.

As shown in Figure 3, the reactivity estimate is highly sensitive to noise, and displays erratic fluctuations with low values of r (with $r = 1$ and $r = 10$), indicating overfitting noisy data. But the estimate becomes too static and unresponsive if $r > 10^4$ as the filter completely ignores the experimental data. Thus, choosing $r = 10^3$ achieves the best trade-off between sensitivity to measurements and robustness to noise. In addition, increasing the ensemble size N from 50 to 500 improved stability and smoothness of the estimates, while further increases provided only marginal benefits.

(a) EnKF estimates of the first and second delayed neutron fraction.

(b) EnKF estimates of the first and second delayed neutron precursor decay constant.

Figure 2. EnKF parameters estimation using a control model.

Figure 3. EnKF estimates of the reactivity for a 600mm control rod withdrawal while varying the scaling factor.

3.2. CROCUS Data

After tuning the EnKF parameters with the control model, it was applied to CROCUS data with the parameters $\sigma_{initial} = 0.5$ (the uncertainty of the dependent variables' initial estimates), $\sigma_{process} = 10^{-3}$ (additional uncertainty after each step), $r = 10^3$, and $N = 500$ to estimate the neutron population $n(t)$, the reactivity $\rho(t)$, and the kinetics parameters ($\Lambda(t)$, $\beta_i(t)$, and $\lambda_i(t)$), with a reactivity insertion

of $\rho = 112 \pm 6$ pcm, corresponding to a 600mm control rod withdrawal. Figure 4a shows the noisy observation data (the measured neutron population) to which the EnKF was applied, and its filtered estimate. Figure 4b–4e summarize the outcome of applying the EnKF, with each plot showing the initial mean of the state variable (dashed black line), how it evolves with filtering, and its 68% confidence interval also evolves. Table I provides the final estimates of reactivity and the kinetics parameters, shows how they changed by applying the EnFK, and shows the reduction in uncertainty achieved by applying the filter.

Figure 4. EnKF estimation of the state and parameters (112 pcm step reactivity insertion scenario).

Figure 4a shows that the EnKF accurately follows the evolution of the neutron population despite noisy observations. It smooths random fluctuations and reproduces the expected growth trend. During the first 50 seconds, the neutron population rises by more than an order of magnitude, consistent with prompt feedback under positive reactivity insertion. Because the neutron population is directly observed, the estimates are strongly constrained and robust. However, reactivity shows a different behavior. Initially set at 112 pcm, the estimate quickly decreases as the filter adapts to the observed neutron

growth. It stabilizes at 102.5 ± 1.4 pcm, reflecting the correction of an initial overestimation rather than a real physical drop. At the same time, the uncertainty shrinks by nearly 77%, yielding increasingly reliable estimates. Other kinetic parameters remain comparatively stable. For example, the mean generation time Λ stays near its initial value, with only a slight drift that later stabilizes. Delayed neutron fractions β_i are initially underestimated but converge towards slightly higher values. Decay constants λ_i remain stable overall, with only small deviations (notably for λ_3) due to noise sensitivity or ensemble limits. The small changes are related to the small uncertainties of these parameters (as seen in Table I), providing little room for adjustment via filtering. The adjustment of these parameters is believed to be caused by the statistical noise inherent to the sampling process in the EnKF.

Table I. EnKF final estimates and relative differences from the initial values, and reductions in uncertainty.

x_i	Unit	EnKF Estimate	σ_{EnKF}	$\frac{\Delta\mu}{\mu_{init}}$	$\frac{\Delta\sigma}{\sigma_{init}}$
ρ	pcm	102.5	1.4	-8.5%	-76.7%
β_1	pcm	24.1	1.2	+1.4%	-3.7%
β_2	pcm	127.0	2.8	+0.7%	-0.8%
β_3	pcm	122.7	2.7	-0.1%	-0.4%
β_4	pcm	284.3	4.1	+0.2%	-2.0%
β_5	pcm	126.4	2.8	+0.1%	-3.6%
β_6	pcm	52.4	1.8	-0.2%	-1.3%
λ_1	s^{-1}	1.33534×10^{-2}	3.07927×10^{-6}	+0.1%	+0.4%
λ_2	s^{-1}	3.26128×10^{-2}	1.00743×10^{-6}	+0.2%	+1.0%
λ_3	s^{-1}	1.21060×10^{-1}	2.04576×10^{-5}	-0.4%	0.0%
λ_4	s^{-1}	3.05664×10^{-1}	1.43187×10^{-4}	+0.3%	+1.5%
λ_5	s^{-1}	8.61043×10^{-1}	6.00646×10^{-4}	0.0%	-1.5%
λ_6	s^{-1}	2.89192×10^0	2.82765×10^{-3}	0.0%	-3.6%
Λ	s	4.68679×10^{-5}	9.70741×10^{-8}	0.0%	+0.3%

4. CONCLUSION

In this work, a comprehensive tool for live reactivity estimation and simultaneous estimation of reactor kinetic parameters was developed using the Ensemble Kalman filter. Such a tool is highly valuable for nuclear reactor start-up, operation, or shut-down, to enhance approach to criticality experiments. The study first focused on applying the Ensemble Kalman filter to a reactivity insertion in a zero-power reactor.

The EnKF accurately tracked the neutron population despite significant noise, reproducing the expected growth trend. During the first 50 seconds, the neutron population increased by more than an order of magnitude. Reactivity estimates stabilized around 102.5 ± 1.4 pcm, correcting the initial overestimate of 112 pcm and reducing uncertainty by 77%. The mean generation time remained stable, while delayed neutron fractions showed small, physically reasonable corrections with prior uncertainties. Decay constants remained nearly constant, consistent with their low nuclear data uncertainty.

This work showed that data assimilation methods can effectively integrate noisy experimental evidence into the point reactor kinetics model and help improve its estimates. From uncertain kinetics parameters (caused by nuclear data uncertainties), the Ensemble Kalman filter incorporated the noisy reactor transient data to produce improved reactivity estimates with lower uncertainty, and adjusted kinetics parameters with lower uncertainty. This study shows the promise of applying data assimilation methods to this kind of dynamic experimental data, which can be expanded in the future to include more complicated effects like reactivity feedback.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. E. Profio. *Experimental Reactor Physics*. John Wiley & Sons, New York, NY, USA (1976).
- [2] N. Thompson, J. Hutchinson, R. Bahran, D. Hayes, W. Myers, J. Arthur, J. Bounds, T. Cutler, D. Dinwiddie, J. Goda, et al. "National Criticality Experiments Research Center (NCERC)-capabilities and recent measurements." In *EPJ Web of Conferences*, volume 239, p. 18003. EDP Sciences (2020).
- [3] J. Leppänen, M. Aufiero, E. Fridman, R. Rachamin, and S. Van Der Marck. "Calculation of effective point kinetics parameters in the Serpent 2 Monte Carlo code." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 65**, pp. 272–279 (2014).
- [4] G. Evensen. "The ensemble Kalman filter: Theoretical formulation and practical implementation." *Ocean dynamics*, **volume 53**(4), pp. 343–367 (2003).
- [5] M. I. Ribeiro. "Kalman and extended kalman filters: Concept, derivation and properties." *Institute for Systems and Robotics*, **volume 43**(46), pp. 3736–3741 (2004).
- [6] E. A. Wan and R. Van Der Merwe. "The unscented Kalman filter for nonlinear estimation." In *Proceedings of the IEEE 2000 adaptive systems for signal processing, communications, and control symposium* (Cat. No. 00EX373), pp. 153–158. Ieee (2000).
- [7] V. Lamirand. "Ten springs of experiments in CROCUS." In *EPJ Web of Conferences*, volume 288, p. 04026. EDP Sciences (2023).
- [8] D. J. Siefman, G. Girardin, A. Rais, A. Pautz, and M. Hursin. "Full Core modeling techniques for research reactors with irregular geometries using Serpent and PARCS applied to the CROCUS reactor." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 85**, pp. 434–443 (2015).
- [9] T. Zhu, A. Vasiliev, H. Ferroukhi, and A. Pautz. "NUSS: A tool for propagating multigroup nuclear data covariances in pointwise ACE-formatted nuclear data using stochastic sampling method." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 75**, pp. 713–722 (2015).